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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE NEPHROTIC SYNDROME
MANAGEMENT: ISKDC VERSUS APN**¹Dr Fatima Noor, ²Dr Zahra Hassan, ³Dr Mariam Mushtaq¹King Edward Medical University, Lahore²King Edward Medical University, Lahore³King Edward Medical University, Lahore**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To compare the recurrence rate between ISKDC and APN protocol in the treatment of nephrotic syndrome.

Study Design: A Randomized Control Trial.

Place and Duration: In the Pediatric unit-II of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020.

Methodology: Total 92 patients, 46 patients in each group, were selected according to non-probability purposive sampling including all nephrotic patients age 1 to 16 years keeping in mind the confounders, then allocating them into group 1 receiving ISKDC and group 2 (APN) randomly and following them for a year. First relapse was the end point of study.

Results In group 1, 4% of patients relapsed in the first month, 13% after three, 35% after six months, and 72% after one year. In group 2, none of the patients relapsed in the first month, 2% after 3 months, 15% after six months, and 30% after one year. The P value was 0.026. Longer duration of steroid use was important in reducing the risk of relapse at the end of the study (relative risk 0.72) (95% CI 0.60-0.90).

Conclusion: APN is superior to ISKDC in preventing nephrotic syndrome recurrence.

Key words: nephrotic, APN, ISKDC, relapses.

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INTRODUCTION:

The term nephrotic syndrome is only fifty to sixty years old, but has been known to man since ancient times. Hippocrates was the first to recognize edema (puffy eyelids) as a manifestation of kidney disease, although it did not extend to various causes. However, the first detailed description of idiopathic children with nephrosis is found in the works of MJC Sabatier. (29%) of patients with renal disease admitted had nephrotic syndrome in the Pakistan study. Nephrotic syndrome is an important chronic disease in children with minimal lesions in most cases. Response to corticosteroid therapy is the best prognostic marker of disease. Initial episodes of nephrotic syndrome are best treated with "long" courses of prednisone therapy (6 weeks of high dose daily prednisone followed by 6 weeks of Prednisone every other day). Various protocols for the treatment of nephrotic syndrome have been proposed, ie ISKDC and APN. In his meta-analysis, Hodson concluded that children with the first episode of steroid-responsive nephrotic syndrome should be treated with prednisone for at least three months, with benefits seen up to seven months of treatment. The present study compares the two protocols ISKDC and APN in the treatment of nephrotic syndrome in terms of treatment efficacy and side effects.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This was a randomized follow-up study conducted at the Pediatric unit-II of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. A total of 92 patients, with 46 patients in each group, selected on a non-probable deliberate basis. Patients included in this study were aged 1 to 16 years with the first sign of nephrotic syndrome or patients with rarely recurrent nephrotic syndrome (4 / yr), steroid-dependent nephrotic syndrome, steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome, and patients with secondary nephrotic syndrome. The admission procedure was through the OPD. Patients were diagnosed on the basis of history, examination, abundant proteinuria > 40 mg / m² / day, hypoalbuminemia 90 ml / min / m². Informed written consent of the parents of selected patients was obtained. Patients were randomized to rule out selection bias. Group I was receiving steroids according to the "ISKDC protocol" ie Every day a steroid at a dose of 60 mg / m² / day for four weeks, then every other day 40 mg / m² / day for four weeks, then stopped suddenly. Group II received steroids according to the "APN protocol" ie Daily steroid at 60 mg / m² / day for six weeks, then every other day 40 mg / m² / day steroid for six weeks and then stopped abruptly. Clinical observation was monthly for a year and the endpoint of the study was the first relapse. The comparisons of the two treatments to determine the relapse rate were made based on certain criteria

such as proteinuria recurrence, hypoalbuminemia and edema (detected around the orbit and foot), treatment complication rate and mortality. The data was analyzed by SPSS version 18.0. Descriptive statistics such as mean \pm standard deviation for variables such as age, weight, serum albumin, and urine protein were calculated. The frequency of the studied variables was calculated, i.e. Nephrotic syndrome relapse in both groups. The difference in recurrence rates in the two groups was statistically tested to see if the difference was statistically significant or not. The value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS:

The age distribution between the two groups is shown in Table 1. The P value was 0.15. The gender distribution between the two groups is shown in the first graph. The mean weight distribution between the two groups is shown in Table 2. The p-value was 0.36. In group 1 (ISKDC), 65% experienced swelling within five days of presentation, 30% within 10 days of presentation, and 4% after ten days. The mean was 1.41 days with a standard deviation of 0.57. While in Group 2 (APN), 72% had swelling within five days of presentation, 24% had swelling within ten days, while 4.3% complained of swelling for more than ten days. The mean was 1.47 days with a standard deviation of 0.58. In group 1 (ISKDC), 100% of children had periorbital edema, 70% had foot edema in addition to periorbital edema, and 4.3% also had sacral edema. In group 2 (APN), 96% had periorbital edema, 65% had foot edema, and 4.3% also had cross-edema. The mean systolic blood pressure in group 1 was 110.52 ± 8.94 , and the diastolic blood pressure was 71.53 ± 6.37 . The mean systolic blood pressure in group 2 was 114.12 ± 9.27 , and the mean diastolic blood pressure was 75.52 ± 7.46 . The P value for systolic blood pressure of 0.08 and diastolic blood pressure was 0.11. In group 1, 9% of patients had serum albumin less than 1 g / L, 48% had serum albumin less than 2 g / L but more than 1 g / L, and 43% had serum albumin more than 2 g / L. But less than 3 g / L. No patient had serum albumin above 3 g / L. The mean was 2.35 g / L with a standard deviation of 0.64 (CI 2.16 to 2.49). In group 2, 13% had serum albumin less than 1 g / L, 46% had serum albumin less than 2 g / L but more than 1 g / L, and 41% had serum albumin less than 3 g / L but more than 2 g / L. As in group 1, neither of them had serum albumin more than 3 g / L. The mean was 2.40 g / L with a standard deviation of 0.61 and (CI of 2.08 to 2.54). In group 1, 17% of the children had 2+ proteins in their urine, 65% had 3+ proteins in their urine, and 17% had 4+ proteins in their urine. The mean was 2.92 with a standard deviation of 0.65. In group 2, 21.7% had proteins 2+ in their urine, 63% had proteins 3+, 15% had proteins 4+ in their urine.

Table 1: Distribution of children of different age groups in Group 1 (ISKDC) and Group 2 (APN)

Age (Years)	Group 1 (ISKDC) (n=46)		Group 2 (APN) (n=46)	
	No.	%	No.	%
<5	19	41.4	21	45.7
6 – 8	22	47.8	20	43.5
9 -12	3	6.5	3	6.5
13 – 16	2	4.3	2	4.3
Mean \pm SD	5.97 \pm 2.56		5.76 \pm 3.03	

Table 2: Mean body weight in both groups

Groups (Protocol)	Mean	Standard deviation	CI >95%	
			Lower bound	Upper bound
Group 1 (ISKDC)	19.41	4.68	18.02	20.80
Group 2 (APN)	19.53	5.72	18.02	20.80
Total	19.53	5.20	17.95	21.35

The mean was 2.86 with a standard deviation of 0.61. Regarding relapses, in group 1 (ISKDC), 4% of patients relapsed in the first month; a further 9% of relapses occurred after three months, for a total relapse of 13%. After six months, 22% of patients relapsed, and total relapse was 35%. At the end of the year, 36% of patients had relapsed, for a total relapse rate of 72%. In group 2 (APN), none of the patients had a relapse by the end of the first month, while 4% of patients relapsed after 3 months, 11% more patients relapsed after six months for a total of 15%. Another 13% relapsed within one year and a total of 28% of patients relapsed. In group 1 (ISKDC), 28% of patients did not relapse, while 70% of patients did not relapse in group 2 (APN) with a P value of 0.026. The P value in those who relapsed was 0.027. Longer duration of steroid use was important in reducing the risk of relapse at the end of the study (relative risk 0.72) (95% confidence interval 0.60-0.90). The total cumulative dose in mg in group 1 was 2.07 and in group 2 it was 3.02, giving a p-value of <0.05. (.002). In group 2 (APN), 5% of patients had a cushingoid appearance and 3% had arterial hypertension. In group 1 (ISKDC), no complications were noted.

DISCUSSION:

There were differences in the age of both groups, with the first group being slightly older, but this difference was not found to be statistically significant. This age was slightly different from other studies in Asia, but this may be due to a somewhat late presentation in this province. More research is needed to prove this, but the study mentioned above was retrospective while our study was prospective. Boys in both groups presented themselves more often than girls. This may be due to gender bias, as in our culture boys see a doctor early. But it may be because it's more common in boys. The important thing is that it is also visible in research conducted abroad. However, in our study it did not prove to be statistically significant. Likewise, it turned out to be irrelevant also in other studies. The mean body weight in both groups was not statistically significant and this is consistent with other international studies. There were no differences in the mean duration of the swelling or the swelling site in both groups. Group two had slightly higher blood pressure than group one, but this cannot be explained on the basis of the steroid intake as it started after the assessment was completed. And this difference also did not turn out to be statistically significant. Serum albumin was comparable in both groups, as was the protein in

urine, which is consistent with international studies. The relapse rates in both groups, which was the focus of this study, were found to be significant. The ISKDC group relapsed twice as often as the APN group. The effect was found regardless of age and gender. The relapse rate was significantly different between the APN and ISKDC groups (0% vs 4% after one month, 2% vs 13% after three months, 15% vs 35% after 6 months, 30% vs 72% after the 1-year timeline plot). This shows that children with nephrosis who were treated over a long period of steroid therapy had fewer relapses and were more likely to remain in remission. Our results are consistent with previous work which shows an inverse relationship between the risk of relapse and the duration of corticosteroid treatment. Therefore, APN is recommended by many centers for treating SSNS in order to obtain better treatment outcomes. It must be acknowledged that the optimal treatment protocol for SSNS is still under discussion and research. It is expected that as research progresses in the future, a more innovative and detailed approach will be available. When the APN report came out in 1988 (APN 3), patients who relapsed with ISKDC or standard risk within the first 6 months were higher (61%) compared to APN (31%) and then named them with a long-term

regimen. Subsequently, many other studies in the late eighties and early nineties also confirmed the same point. Finally, in their historical meta-analysis, Hodson et al. Reported that the combined results of these studies recommended that the initial treatment of SSNS should be at least 3 months. All of this is in line with our study. This study was conducted over a period of one year compared to other studies that assessed the recurrence rate over six months. Our study is important because, unlike other studies, it is a prospective study and the two compared groups were similar in terms of clinical features, serum albumin, blood pressure, etc.

CONCLUSION:

APN surpasses ISKDC in preventing relapse in children with nephrotic syndrome.

REFERENCES:

1. Deschênes, Georges, Marina Vivarelli, and Licia Peruzzi. "Variability of diagnostic criteria and treatment of idiopathic nephrotic syndrome across European countries." *European journal of pediatrics* 176, no. 5 (2019): 647-654.
2. Pasini, Andrea, Elisa Benetti, Giovanni Conti, Luciana Ghio, Marta Lepore, Laura Massella, Daniela Molino et al. "The Italian Society for Pediatric Nephrology (SINePe) consensus document on the management of nephrotic syndrome in children: Part I-Diagnosis and treatment of the first episode and the first relapse." *Italian Journal of Pediatrics* 43, no. 1 (2019): 41.
3. Schijvens, A. M., Eiske M. Dorresteyn, Nel Roeleveld, Rob Ter Heine, Joanna AE van Wijk, Antonia HM Bouts, M. G. Keijzer-Veen, Nicole CAJ van de Kar, L. P. W. J. Van Den Heuvel, and M. F. Schreuder. "REducing STERoids in Relapsing Nephrotic syndrome: the RESTERN study—protocol of a national, double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled, non-inferiority intervention study." *BMJ open* 7, no. 9 (2020): e018148.
4. Noone, Damien G., Kazumoto Iijima, and Rulan Parekh. "Idiopathic nephrotic syndrome in children." *The Lancet* 392, no. 10141 (2020): 61-74.
5. Deschênes, Georges, Claire Dossier, and Julien Hogan. "Treating the idiopathic nephrotic syndrome: are steroids the answer?." *Pediatric Nephrology* 34, no. 5 (2019): 777-785.
6. Hodson, Elisabeth M., Sophia C. Wong, Narelle S. Willis, and Jonathan C. Craig. "Interventions for idiopathic steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome in children." *Cochrane database of systematic reviews* 10 (2019).
7. Liu, Isaac D., Narelle S. Willis, Jonathan C. Craig, and Elisabeth M. Hodson. "Interventions for idiopathic steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome in children." *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 11 (2019).
8. Shah, Syed Raza, Areeba Altaf, Mohammad Hussham Arshad, Anum Mari, Sahir Noorani, Eraj Saeed, Areesh Amir Mevawalla, Zaiyn Ul Haq, and Muhammad Ehsan Faquih. "Use of cyclosporine therapy in steroid resistant nephrotic syndrome (SRNS): a review." *Global journal of health science* 8, no. 4 (2019): 136.
9. Hodson, Elisabeth M., Stephen I. Alexander, and Nicole Graf. "Steroid sensitive nephrotic syndrome." In *Pediatric Kidney Disease*, pp. 419-453. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2019.
10. Basu, Biswanath, Suman Bhattacharyya, Shilpita Barua, Abhisek Naskar, and Birendranath Roy. "Efficacy of body weight vs body surface area-based prednisolone regimen in nephrotic syndrome." *Clinical and Experimental Nephrology* (2020): 1-8.
11. Al Talhi, AbdulHadi, Khalid Al Saran, ElTayeb Taha Osman, AbdulAziz Al Shatri, Mutawakil Osman, and Khalid Mirza. "A randomized study on a 3-month versus a 7-month prednisolone regimen for the initial episode of childhood idiopathic nephrotic syndrome at a large Saudi center." *International Journal of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine* 5, no. 1 (2020): 18-23.
12. Franke, Ingo, Malik Aydin, Corinna Elke Llamas Lopez, Lisa Kurylowicz, Rainer Ganschow, Michael Lentze, and Mark Born. "The incidence of the nephrotic syndrome in childhood in Germany." *Clinical and experimental nephrology* 22, no. 1 (2019): 126-132.
13. Thalagahagoda, R. S., A. HH M. Jayaweera, U. I. Karunadasa, and A. S. Abeyagunawardena. "Therapies for steroid-sensitive nephrotic syndrome." *Asian Journal of Pediatric Nephrology* 1, no. 2 (2020): 56.
14. Hodson, Elisabeth M., Stephen I. Alexander, and Nicole Graf. "Steroid Sensitive Nephrotic." *Pediatric Kidney Disease* (2019): 419.
15. Rheault, Michelle N. "Nephrotic syndrome: updates and approaches to treatment." *Current Treatment Options in Pediatrics* 2, no. 2 (2019): 94-103.